

**DIGITIZATION OF PRIMARY SCHOOLS THROUGH COMPUTER
MANAGED INSTRUCTION PROGRAMME IN THE TEACHING OF
SCIENCE IN ILORIN METROPOLIS**

Abdulazeez, Bolanle Tawakalt-Anu

Department of Science Education, Faculty of Education, Al-Hikmah University,
Ilorin, Nigeria.

0009-0001-5214-4394

Email: bolanleabdulazeez@gmail.com

Bello, Zakariyau Adebayo PhD

Department of Integrated Science, Kwara State College of Education, Ilorin

Orcid ID: 0000-0001-8001-2404

Email: Zakbay26@gmail.com

Shogbesan, Yusuf Olayinka PhD

Department of Arts and Social Science Education, Faculty of Education, Al-
Hikmah University, Ilorin, Nigeria.

0000-0002-1741-1370

Email: yoshogbesan@alhikmah.edu.ng

Awolola, Oluwafemi Fadesewa

Department of Computer Science, Kwara State College of Education, Ilorin

Email: oluwafemi.ibilola@gmail.com

Olaofe, Abayomi Israel

Lagos State University, Ojo, Lagos

orcid.org/0009-0003-5152-9000

Email: olaofeabayomi@ymail.com

ABSTRACT

This study investigated the influence of digitization, on Computer Managed Instruction Programme in the teaching of science in primary education within Kwara State. Employing a descriptive survey research design, 448 primary school teachers participated in the study. Data were analysed using frequency counts and percentages. The findings revealed a predominant adoption of a teacher-centered digitization approach, with readily available digital materials considered adequate for science instruction. Notably, approximately 90.2% of teachers exhibited proficiency in tablet usage, indicating a positive influence of the Kwara LEARN programme on science teaching. The study discovered the prevalent teacher-centered approach to digitization in Kwara State, the sufficiency of available digital materials for teaching science, and the positive influence of digitization on primary school science teaching. It was recommended that ensuring widespread availability of digital materials in all primary school in Kwara State is imperative for effective science teaching in primary schools.

Keywords: Digitization, Science teaching, Primary school, Kwara LEARN

INTRODUCTION

Education is the process of acquiring information and the growth resulting from it enables individuals to reach better states of existence. Abdulazeez (2017) notes that a person's perspective changes due to behavioral changes during the educational process, emphasizing that learning how to lead a better life is the essence of education. According to the Collins English Dictionary (2022), education strengthens one's capacity for thinking and judgment, and prepares individuals for mature life. Abdulrahman (2013) asserts that education is the cornerstone for a nation's development across economic, political, social, and human dimensions.

In the modern world, the teaching and study of science encapsulate the essence of education. Khan (2019) advocates for the use of technology in education, particularly to accommodate diverse learning paces among pupils. The integration of technology into education should reflect its pervasive influence, especially in science education. However, this integration should align with the broader context of digitization in primary education, exemplified by the Computer Managed Instruction program, Kwara LEARN. In streamlining the discussion to create a more coherent narrative will enhance the overall flow of the presentation, ensuring that insights on the influence of technology in education align

seamlessly with the broader context of digitization in primary education, as discussed earlier.

According to Wang and Reeves (2003), instructors' adoption of technology requires accessibility, support for instructor control, and pedagogical flexibility. Rutto (2014) and LeCun (2022) identify factors influencing the use of Computer Assisted Instructions, including ICT availability, teacher preparedness, and teaching experience. The rapid evolution of computer-related technology necessitates educators' awareness of current and future technical requirements (Kibagendi, 2014). Efficiently bridging diverse technologies to support learning is crucial. Computers, equipped with integrated visuals, print materials, and computer-managed instruction, play a pivotal role in this regard. Computer-managed instruction (CMI), as defined by Abdallah (2019), guides students, maintains records, and supports instructional decision-making. Teachers' dedication is crucial in fostering positive outcomes, and initiatives like KwaraLEARN aim to equip them with digital tools and establish transparency in classrooms and schools (Adaramaja, 2022).

In aligning the discussion to emphasize the symbiotic relationship

between technology and education, particularly in the context of primary education digitization, enhances understanding and facilitates effective implementation of educational technologies. The educational landscape in Kwara is undergoing a transformative shift, with traditional teaching approaches making way for modern strategies and resources such as computers in classrooms. In today's increasingly digitalized world, the significance and value of incorporating technology, specifically computer-managed instruction (CMI), into the teaching process cannot be overstated.

According to Onyio (2021), the Federal Government recognizes the pivotal role of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in education and emphasizes its importance in achieving various national educational objectives, including the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the National Policy on Education, the Ministerial Strategic Plan: Education for Change, and the National Vision of the Federal Republic of Nigeria. The urgency for computer-managed instruction and the digitization of education in Nigeria, as highlighted by researchers like Asogwa (2011) and Yaya and Adeeko (2016), is a response to ongoing sector reforms

aimed at enhancing effectiveness. Notably, Professor Shehu Raheem Adaramaja, the Chairman of the Kwara State Universal Basic Education Board (KWSUBEB), articulates the government's vision for KwaraLEARN. The initiative seeks to elevate primary school outcomes by transforming learning in all classrooms and ensuring that every child has access to excellent and well-supported teachers.

Given this context, the study aims to investigate the impact of the digitization of primary education, particularly the introduction of computer-managed instruction, on scientific instruction in Kwara's primary schools. The focus is on understanding the local implications and practical outcomes of incorporating CMI into the teaching methodologies within the state.

Objectives of the Study

The objective of this study is to investigate the impact of digitization in primary education, specifically through computer-managed instruction in Kwara State, Nigeria. The study seeks to:

1. identify and assess the presence of digital materials available for instructional delivery in primary education within Kwara state.
2. assess whether the digital materials available in Kwara State are sufficient

and appropriate for teaching science in primary schools.

3. determine the of digitization, particularly through KwaraLearn, on the teaching of science in primary schools across Kwara State.

Research Questions

The study answered the following research questions:

- 1) What digital materials are available for instructional delivery in Kwara State?
- 2) To what extent do the available digital materials support the teaching of science in Kwara State?
- 3) What is the influence of digitization on the teaching of science in primary schools in Kwara State?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This survey-based descriptive research examined the implementation of computer-managed instruction through KwaraLearn, on scientific instruction in public primary schools in Kwara State, Nigeria.

Participants

The study focused on all public primary school teachers in Kwara State, Nigeria, with a population estimated at 4,300 teachers across

sixteen primary schools in the city of Ilorin according Kwara state ministry of education statistic (2023). A random sample of 448 respondents was selected to ensure the generalizability of the results.

Instrumentation

The questionnaire titled "Influence of Digitization on Science Teaching in Primary School Questionnaire (IDSTLPSQ)" was utilized for data collection. Adapted from Rutto (2014), the questionnaire comprised 30 items categorized into three sections: Section A covered teachers' biographical information, Section B focused on digital device availability, adequacy, and usage, while Section C addressed the influence of digitization on the teaching of science.

Validity of the Instrument

The questionnaire's validity was ensured through adaptation from a previously validated instrument and consultation with experts to verify its content relevance.

Reliability of the Instrument

The reliability of the questionnaire was established through pilot testing with a subset of the target population to assess consistency and coherence

of responses. The reliability index of 0.79 obtained indicated higher reliability

Procedure for Data Collection

The instrument was distributed to the randomly selected respondents, focusing on gathering information regarding teachers' school affiliation, gender, highest qualification, years of experience, availability and adequacy of digital devices, and the perceived impact of digitization on science instruction. Informed consent was obtained from each participating teacher prior to their inclusion in the study.

Ethical approval was obtained from relevant educational authorities, ensuring the protection of participants' rights and confidentiality throughout the research process.

Data Analysis

Descriptive statistical methods such as frequencies and percentages were employed to analyze the gathered data. These methods aimed to provide insights into prevailing trends and patterns regarding the influence of digitalization on science teaching in primary education.

RESULTS

Table 1: Characteristics of Primary School Teachers

Variables	Options	Number of respondents	Percentage %
Gender	Male	186	41.52
	Female	262	58.48
Academic qualification	Qualified	408	91.01
	Unqualified	40	8.92
Teaching Experience	Experienced	398	88.84
	Less Experienced	50	11.16

Table 1 showed that the sample included 448 respondents, 408 respondents (41.52%) were male while 262 (58.48%) respondents were females, 124 were qualified (91.01%) and 40 were unqualified (8.92%),

398 respondents (88.84%) were experienced while only 50 were less experienced.

Research Question One: What digital materials are available for instructional delivery in Kwara State?

Table 2: Digital Materials Available for Instructional Delivery in Kwara State

S/N	Item Statements	Yes	No	Remark
1.	Kwara LEARN tablets	96.00%	4.00%	Available
2.	Print materials	92.90%	7.10%	Available
3.	Appropriate Textbooks	88.84%	11.16%	Available
4.	CDs/DVDS relevant forteaching science	13.17%	86.83%	Unavailable
5.	Digital literacy Centre	21.42%	78.58%	Unavailable
6.	Networked computers	9.60%	90.40%	Unavailable
7.	Internet connected computers	21.42%	78.58%	Unavailable

Table 2 showed that 96% of the respondents (430 teachers) indicated that Kwara LEARN tablets were given to them and are readily available, 92.90% of the respondents (416 teachers) indicated that print materials such as charts are available for the teaching of science, 88.84% of respondents (398 teachers) indicated that Appropriate Textbooks available and allocated to students for learning science. Meanwhile, only 13.17% of respondents (59 teachers) agreed that CDs/DVDS relevant for teaching science were available in their

schools, 21.42% of the teachers (96 teachers) pointed out that Digital literacy Centers are available in their schools while 9.60% of respondents (43 teachers) indicated that Networked computers are available, 21.42% of respondents (96 teachers) indicated that Internet connected computers are available for teaching science in public primary schools in Kwara state.

- 4) **Research Question Two:** To what extent do the available digital materials support the teaching of science in Kwara State?

Table 3: Digitization of Teaching of Science in Primary Schools in Kwara State

S/N	Items	X	SD	Remark
1.	Kwara LEARN tablets	3.52	0.80	Adequate
2.	Print materials	3.11	0.87	Adequate
3.	Appropriate Textbooks	3.05	0.99	Adequate
4.	CDs/DVDS relevant for teaching science	2.29	0.35	Inadequate
5.	Digital literacy Centre	2.32	0.51	Inadequate
6.	Networked computers	3.31	0.91	Adequate
7.	Internet connected computers	2.03	0.48	Inadequate
Weighted average		2.80	0.70	Adequate

Table 3 showed that the respondents indicated that Kwara LEARN tablets (mean=3.52), print materials such as charts (mean=3.11), Appropriate Textbooks (mean=3.05), and

Networked computers (mean=3.31) are adequate for teaching science in public primary schools in Kwara state. While CDs/DVDS relevant for teaching science, Digital literacy

Centre and Internet connected computers are inadequate with means between 2.03 and 2.32 which is lower than the 2.5 benchmark for adequacy on the four-point scale.

Research Question Three:
What is the influence of digitization on the teaching of science in primary schools in Kwara state?

Table 4: Influence of Digitization of Teaching of Science in Primary Schools in Kwara State

S/N	Item Statements	X	SD	Remark
1.	My content knowledge of science has improved since I started teaching with the Kwara LEARN tablet	3.41	0.71	Agreed
2.	I am more comfortable teaching science with the Kwara LEARN tablet	3.33	0.80	Agreed
3.	I find it difficult to teach science content from the Kwara LEARN tablet	1.54	0.68	Disagreed
4.	I find it uncomfortable to teach science with the Kwara LEARN tablet	2.23	0.62	Disagreed
5.	My students learning outcomes have greatly improved since I started teaching with the Kwara LEARN tablet	3.28	0.85	Agreed
Weighted average		2.76	0.73	Agreed

From Table 4, respondents indicated that Kwara LEARN tablets increased their content knowledge (mean=3.41), made them comfortable teaching science (mean=3.33), and

improved students learning outcomes (mean=3.23). While they disagreed with the items about difficulty to use the Kwara LEARN tablets for teaching science with means between

1.54 and 2.23 which is lower than the 2.5 benchmark for agreement on the four-point scale. This means that the influence of digitization on the teaching of science in primary schools is positive.

Discussion

The Kwara LEARN initiative has received praise from the teachers in the state's primary schools. They feel that by eliminating the need for lesson notes, an easier attendance record, and a stress-free lesson plan, the job stress has been decreased. Since using the Kwara LEARN tablet in their classes, teachers have reported that their content understanding of science has increased and that they feel more at ease using it. Printed items, such as charts and pertinent textbooks, were available as digital resources. The Kwara LEARN tablets for teachers, the head teacher's rating and access control tablet, assistant head teachers' teacher evaluation tablet, and a digital literacy center in certain schools within different local government. They indicated that students learning outcomes have greatly improved since the program started. The Kwara LEARN tablet was found out to be Teacher-centered instead of being Student-centered, Teachers indicated that they received training in batches and some of them are yet to receive the training. In the same vain, Teachers lamented that the timing

pre-set for the tasks are too short to achieve those tasks. Some Teachers indicated that they found it difficult to relate to some of the science content because they are not science teachers by training. All the teachers indicated that sometimes, there are connectivity issues.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that; A Teacher-centered form of digitization was adopted in Kwara state, digital materials are available for instructional delivery. The available digital materials were adequate for teaching science in primary schools. The digitization of primary education in Kwara state has a positive influence on the teaching of science in primary schools.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. The government should review the program to accommodate a Student-centered approach.
2. The digital materials should be made available to all the primary school teachers in the 16 local government areas in Kwara state.
3. Adequate timing should be assigned to the tasks given for

effective teaching of science in primary schools in Kwara state.

4. There should be prompt response to connectivity issue. Above all, based on existing realities, the programme should be modified as soon as possible.

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